

Interview with Pianist Kayoko Morimoto

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CoolJapan.es

Good morning, readers. Today we bring you an interview with Kayoko Morimoto Otani, a very special figure for the CoolJapan.es team, as she has collaborated with us for years at events attended by our colleagues, working as a Japanese interpreter. However, her main specialisation lies in musical performance—specifically as a pianist. In recent years, she has also collaborated in promoting other specialists and professionals in the music sector alongside the Film Music Festival team—organisers of the MOSMA festival, which CoolJapan.es attends every year with great enthusiasm.

Together with Kayoko Morimoto, we have interviewed other professionals such as Kenji Kawai and Tarō Iwashiro, and after following her work closely, we felt it was time to dedicate some well-deserved attention to her. This is especially fitting, as she embodies the spirit of CoolJapan.es: individuals who serve as a bridge between Japan and Spain.

That said, we must warn readers not to take the title of this interview too literally, as Kayoko is not only a pianist, but a truly multifaceted professional, as will become clear below. Born in Osaka, Japan, she began her musical career in her hometown, where she graduated as a pianist from the Osaka College of Music under the guidance of the renowned Takejirō Hirai, achieving excellent academic results. Always interested in international and cosmopolitan music, she chose Spain to continue both her professional career and her education, studying under the acclaimed pianist Manuel Carra. In Madrid, she completed her studies in Piano and Chamber Music at the Real Conservatory of Music, where she was awarded the End-of-Degree Prize in recognition of her outstanding academic performance.

Morimoto has specialised primarily as an accompanying pianist, a discipline that requires not only mastery of the piano itself, but also a deep understanding of other instruments and how they interact within an ensemble. Throughout her career, she has accompanied virtually every instrument found in an orchestra.

The artist Kayoko Morimoto

In addition to her work as an accompanist, she has performed as a soloist, in duos and trios, and with various chamber music ensembles. She is also an experienced educator, having participated—either as a teacher or accompanist—in numerous programs, including the National Music Course of Quintanar de la Orden, the European Saxophone University in San Juan and Almagro, the Saxophone Courses of San Lorenzo del Escorial and Buñol, and the Contemporary Music Course in Alcorcón.

She has also served as a piano teacher at the Conservatory of Music in Arganda del Rey (Madrid). Furthermore, she has been involved in the selection of members for the European Union Youth Orchestra and has collaborated with ensembles such as the Villa de Madrid Chamber Choir and the Complutense University Choir, as well as with the Faculty of Music at Universidad Alfonso X el Sabio. She has performed solo recitals both in Japan and Madrid, and has toured in regions such as Andalusia, Gran Canaria, and Strasbourg, among others.

Kayoko Morimoto was also a member of the instrumental group “Sax Ensemble,” with which she performed in prestigious venues such as the National Auditorium, the Reina Sofía Music School, the Monumental Theatre, the Círculo de Bellas Artes, the Royal Academy of Fine Arts of San Fernando, the Conde Duque Cultural Center, the Palau de la Música in Valencia, the Principal Theatre of Palma de Mallorca, the Generalife in Granada, the University of Montreal, the University of Surrey, London, the Centre Georges Pompidou, and the Bordeaux Conservatory, as well as in many of the most important contemporary music festivals in Spain. The “Sax Ensemble,” of which she was a member, was awarded the National Music Prize in 1997. Morimoto possesses extensive knowledge of the saxophone repertoire, having worked for over thirty years with expert saxophonists, including internationally renowned Spanish musicians such as Roque Baños.

Morimoto is an energetic and tireless professional, and as if all of the above were not enough, she has also worked in recent years as a Japanese interpreter, thanks to her excellent command of Spanish. She is an active collaborator in film music events such as MOSMA, where the CoolJapan.es team first met her in person. As will become clear throughout this interview, she not only shares insights into her professional work—let us remember that she is also a teacher—but also offers valuable perspectives on music and the piano more broadly. This is especially appreciated for readers who may not be experts in music, myself included, as I am a visual artist and the author of this interview. I therefore apologise in advance to Kayoko if at any point my questions reveal a lack of technical precision.

Interview with Kayoko Morimoto

Cool Japan: First of all, thank you for your time, Kayoko. We know you are a prolific person and very busy. To start, we would like you to tell us about your career. How long have you been interested in working in the world of music? Was this something you wanted since you were a child?

Kayoko Morimoto: Hello, CoolJapan.es and dear readers. First of all, I would like to thank you for including me, and especially Andrés. I attended MOSMA merely as a language interpreter, without playing a single note on the piano during the festival. I didn't have much experience as a language interpreter. Nevertheless, I felt very welcomed and appreciated by the entire team and collaborators, including Andrés. He

even gave me the opportunity to promote myself by interviewing me as a pianist. I feel extremely fortunate. Thank you very much!

As I said, yes, I am a professional pianist. I began studying piano at the age of five. I couldn't explain why, but from the very beginning, I knew I wanted to do it. I was also greatly guided and supported by my parents. My mother would take me to piano concerts almost every month from the time I started. It would take over an hour to get to any concert hall, but for me, that was normal. Eventually, I entered a university of music and graduated. In my final year, I briefly considered becoming an actress. That was the only time I doubted my profession, although, as you can see, my lifelong passion has always been art and expressing myself through it. I studied for a year at a dramatic arts academy but ultimately decided to continue with piano. Nevertheless, I gained valuable lessons from that experience, such as the idea of motivating words—behind every line you speak in theatre, there must be a reason: who you are, where you come from, why you say those words—which can be perfectly applied to piano performance.

When I decided to continue with the piano, I wanted to leave Japan. I was not entirely satisfied with the philosophy and situation of musicians there. Some classmates studied intensively and performed at a very high technical level, but for me, something was missing: feeling the music. When thinking about where to go, I preferred countries with fewer Japanese people. Competing with them was already enough at the university I attended.

I was interested in nationalist music, particularly Russian and Spanish. At that time, which was still the end of the Soviet Union, I did not dare to go to Russia. At the same time, I was drawn to perfecting my understanding of Spanish music, which then—and still now—is relatively unknown to Japanese musicians. Eventually, I chose to come here. Upon arriving to deepen my study of Spanish nationalist music, I met a teacher who changed almost completely the way I approached the piano, not limiting me to Spanish music. I also felt identified and happy when I began performing with other musicians. Here, this is called being a “pianista acompañante” —collaborative pianist. For me, it is another specialty, distinct from being a soloist in chamber music.

Excelling in one does not necessarily mean excelling in the other. I am very happy and proud of my work. It is also gratifying when top-level musicians praise me and rely on me. Similarly, when my students show satisfaction and trust, it provides me with significant moral support.

As you can see, my vocation for music began in childhood, and I have dedicated my life to it, although working as a language interpreter is enjoyable. Who knows what the future holds [laughs].

CJ: Has the piano always been your chosen instrument? If so, could you tell us what fascinates you about this grand instrument? Who are your favourite pianists and composers? Which piano performers have left the greatest impression on you, and with whom do you feel most connected?

KM: In Japan, it is quite common for girls to study piano from an early age—at least in my generation—although it is less common for them to learn other instruments. Usually, most children stop after three or four years. Therefore, my choice of the piano might have been circumstantial, but fortunately, it was the right one. I like this instrument, although I also enjoy string and percussion instruments.

What I love about the piano is, above all, its polyphonic character. One can perform orchestral music using just this instrument. It also allows the creation of many timbres. I enjoy recreating transparent timbres and blending them with other instruments. However, it can also produce harder, more intense sounds. And, of course, I can perform chamber music with almost any instrument.

When I discovered Spanish music, which changed my life, the representative pianist of this repertoire was Alicia de Larrocha—which already gives away my age [laughs]. I listened to every Spanish music record by her that I could get. I admire pianists or musicians who express their passions, such as Nelson Freire. Regarding contemporary pianists, I admire their technical perfection and musicality, but I prefer more “human” interpretations.

CJ: What are your favourite musical genres? We understand that since you have been associated with the saxophone for years—given its particular association with jazz—this genre might be among them. Do you have any jazz performers who have particularly influenced your career?

KM: To clarify, the “Sax Ensemble” is not a jazz group. It has nothing to do with jazz. It is a contemporary music group within classical music, with a variable line-up that could range from a saxophone quartet to ensembles including saxophone, piano, percussion, strings, and other wind instruments. Its main activity was premiering works by contemporary classical composers. I like jazz, but unfortunately, I haven’t had the opportunity to expand my knowledge or experience in this field. I only had the chance to perform music by Gershwin or Claude Bolling.

CJ: Are you also enthusiastic about film music and soundtracks? Given your collaboration with festivals such as Málaga’s MOSMA, we would like to think you are, and you have even worked with Roque Baños, a Spanish composer of international renown. What has your experience been with this type of music?

KM: My participation at MOSMA as a language interpreter has been by chance. One year, someone contacted me because they were seeking a replacement for three days, as the person originally hired could not attend the entire week. I had never worked as an interpreter before and did not know how the work would go, but I was excited about the idea and found it fun. I must admit that it was an unknown world for me—another environment, more active and directly connected to musical demands. I would like to explore this field further, but gradually.

Roque Baños is a very old friend. I knew him before he began his career as a film composer. He had just returned from the United States after finishing his studies at the Juilliard School of Music. He is an exceptional saxophonist, and at that time, he was making his way as a saxophonist. That is how we met, because I was a répétiteur specialising in saxophone music. Later, at the start of his career as a film composer, I participated in some of his projects. But then he expanded his work internationally and moved residence, and we lost contact. In fact, thanks to MOSMA, we have reconnected. Roque is a musician with incredible talent, rarely found in Spain or even worldwide. I am very glad that he has received the recognition he deserves and that I have had the chance to reunite with him.

CJ: Of the various abilities that the piano possesses—thanks, of course, to the skill of its performer—one is its capacity to interact with other instruments. Yet its power as a solo instrument is undeniable, being unique in its class. In your opinion, in which situation is the piano most interesting and challenging: as a solo instrument or as part of an ensemble?

KM: As I mentioned before, for me, being a solo pianist and a chamber music pianist are entirely different things. The courage required to face an audience alone and express oneself as the sole performer is admirable. However, when I connect with other musicians performing in the same piece and feel a sort of sixth-sense communication, creating another dimension that I could never imagine alone, it is an extraordinary pleasure.

Kayoko Morimoto playing the piano during one of her many performances

The piano can imitate almost any other instrument, which is why, from Beethoven onwards, piano music was often composed with orchestral sonorities in mind. In an era without sound recording, the piano was responsible for disseminating orchestral works to distant or small venues. This also means it is an instrument that accommodates almost any instrumental combination in terms of timbre.

For me, the joy of chamber music comes when we all feel as one. For this, all members must have such sensitivity and ear that they can capture each other's intention and feeling at every moment. Naturally, it is much easier when everyone shares similar musical preferences. When I feel that we are performing as a single entity, sharing the entire experience, that pleasure is unparalleled for me.

CJ: We find it particularly interesting that your relationship with other instruments has been especially close to the saxophone. You were part of the “Sax-Ensemble” and other projects such as “Wasei Duo.” In these projects, you work closely with the saxophone, and both before and afterwards, you have collaborated on piano alongside this instrument. How do you experience collaborating on piano with the saxophone, given that these are two instruments that are truly complex to pair? Is the saxophone an instrument you find particularly engaging, or are there others that excite you aside from the piano, your speciality?

KM: My story with the saxophone is nothing extraordinary. When I was finishing my piano studies here in Spain, a percussionist called me to accompany him for an audition. One of his colleagues from the Madrid municipal band, a saxophonist, heard us and liked my performance. He invited me to play with him. I do not recall if we ultimately performed anything substantial, but through word of mouth, I began to make a name for myself in the saxophone world. The great composer and pianist Sebastián Maríné invited me to replace him in Sax-Ensemble when he decided to leave the group. I felt very fortunate and well welcomed, and before I knew it, I had been part of the ensemble for 23 years. Since then, my relationship with the instrument naturally strengthened.

The saxophone has a very wide dynamic range. Therefore, it is not necessary to play louder than the music requires, so as not to overpower another instrument. This allows me to express myself more freely. Moreover, the instrument can produce a variety of sound effects, enabling the creation of new sonorities in collaboration with the piano. With Wasei Duo, we sought a new repertoire that was simultaneously enjoyable to listen to. We premiered many works during the group’s active years. Composers began contacting us, interested in the recordings we published, to have us premiere their works. Unfortunately, this project could not last very long.

CJ: We see that you are a multifaceted person with many skills. You are not only a pianist but also a teacher, répétiteur, collaborative pianist, researcher, and Japanese interpreter... Of all the tasks you are capable of performing, which do you value most? Which is your favourite work?

KM: As I have expressed from the beginning, I love making music in a group setting—that is, chamber music. It does not matter whether I play with professionals or students, particularly those at the advanced degree level.

At this level, students do not always perform worse than professionals. It is almost the opposite: advanced students dedicate themselves to studying their instrument all day and are more technically active. Of course, professionals who perform in concerts are in a different league. In any case, I am fascinated by performing with musicians, whether in a class or a concert, and when I feel deeply connected with the musician(s) in the group, I experience immense happiness. Being a language interpreter has been something that happened to me by chance.

I have not considered pursuing it professionally yet. Nevertheless, my experiences at MOSMA have been so rewarding, and I have felt so accepted, that I would not mind expanding this role if the opportunity arises. So who knows, in five years I might be saying that my favourite work is as a language interpreter [laughs].

CJ: Given your deep and long-standing connection with Spain, could you tell us why you decided to study there and what led you to continue working in that land? As a Japanese professional, you are especially interesting to Spaniards because you bridge Japanese and Western culture, and in particular our own.

KM: I have already recounted the story of why I decided to come to Spain to further my studies, so I will not repeat myself. However, I would like to share that initially I noticed many cultural clashes here, such as punctuality or informality. Here, if someone says they will call you the next day, the only certainty is that they will not call the next day—it may be never, or perhaps a week later. The reason given is that they are not machines, and plans change.

It also happened to me several times that someone I considered a close friend would suddenly distance themselves without apparent reason and, of course, without any explanation. Often, after some short period without contact, it was impossible that I had offended them in any way. At first, I found it difficult to understand, but then I realised not all Spaniards are the same. Here, everyone acts and expresses opinions very independently. That, to me, is true Spanish culture. The key is to find people with whom you genuinely feel at ease.

Regarding music, Japanese and Spanish music appear very different. In my opinion, Eastern culture turns inward, while Western culture turns outward. Eastern culture tends to explore the inner mind and does not value overt demonstration. Rather, those with mental depth express it implicitly, and the listener must understand it from within. In the West, it is the opposite. Performers must express themselves at 120 per cent, exaggerating everything for the audience to understand fully. Yet because the approaches are so different, I sometimes feel the two cultures are surprisingly close, as if they were points on the surface of a sphere. Flamenco, with its intense emotional expression, is very similar to “Enka,” a form of Japanese popular music.

CJ: Following up on the previous question, do you have any Japanese or Spanish performers or composers whom you particularly admire or take as a reference?

KM: I came here because I loved Spanish nationalist music, such as the works of Albéniz, Granados, Falla, or Turina. As I have said, I greatly admired Alicia de Larrocha for her passionate interpretations. Among contemporary composers, I enjoy the works of Mario Carro, Hache Costa, and Héctor Parra. As for Japanese composers, I am fond of the works of the great Tōru Takemitsu, Takashi Yoshimatsu, and Ryōta Ishikawa, who have a line of contemporary romanticism. After having performed so much contemporary music, I realise that deep down, I am very romantic [laughs].

CJ: To conclude, we would like you to tell us about the projects you are currently involved in and what the future holds for you. Could you share any upcoming projects or future works? Of course, seeing you again at future editions of MOSMA would be a pleasure.

KM: I want to continue with Erasmus projects across several European countries, organising concerts and musical activities.

Another activity I love is participating in the Saxophone Festival of Villa de Teror—Gran Canaria, Canary Islands—which has become something of a tradition, and I enjoy it greatly. In this festival, top-level teachers are invited for the annual masterclass, held in the beautiful surroundings of Teror with unbeatable climate.

In the coming years, I also have plans to perform some concerts in Japan, which I am very excited about. Last academic year [referring to 2018], personal matters kept me busy, and I could not participate freely in other activities. I hope to resume them this year. I would like to continue performing with my esteemed friends, such as the saxophonist Andrés Gomis—the founder of Sigma Project—or the flautist Juana Guillem—until a couple of years ago, principal of the Spanish National Orchestra. I would be delighted to receive offers to perform with them. Although I could not participate in this year’s edition for the reasons I mentioned, of course I would love to continue collaborating with MOSMA as a language interpreter and, if possible, also as a musician, which is my main profession.

Acknowledgements

We would like to extend our gratitude to Kayoko Morimoto herself, for her time, and for her immense patience and kindness in participating in this interview with us. The interview had to be conducted in writing over several months—hence why some questions and topics may have seemed repetitive to her. Given the endless professional activity in which she is constantly engaged, the fact that she was able to dedicate such an extensive interview to us is sincerely appreciated.

Without further ado, we leave you, via this link, with Morimoto herself on video, alongside fellow musician Andrés Gomis. We highly recommend that you take a look—or rather, a listen—at her performance, as evidence of what we have described about her, and of how piano and other instruments work together in complete harmony through the talent of their performers.

It goes without saying that we strongly recommend experiencing Morimoto in person whenever you have the opportunity.

Sources

- **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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